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Computer-aided identification of trihalomethane degradation by haloalkane dehalogenase DhaA from *Rhodococcus* sp.

M.M. Pereira*, R.C. Martins

University of Coimbra, CIEPQPF – Chemical Engineering Processes and Forest Products Research Center, Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Sciences and Technology, Rua Silvio Lima, Polo II, 3030-790 Coimbra, Portugal.

*matheus@eq.uc.pt

The work aims to investigate the potential of DhaA from *Rhodococcus* sp. as biocatalyst for trihalomethanes (THMs) removal from drinking water. For this, a computational protocol for enzymatic tunnel/access prediction and molecular docking analysis of substrates/products was carried out. The three-dimensional structure of DhaA was analyzed using CaverWeb 1.0 to identify the most promising tunnels for ligand transport. The identified tunnels were analyzed and the ligand transport capacity using ligand energy analysis of substrates/products was evaluated. The binding energies of each ligand (water, chloroform, dichloromethane, chloromethanediol, hydrochloric acid, and orthoformic acid) were calculated based on the sequence of complete dehalogenation with DhaA as a biocatalyst. According to the binding energies profiles, Tunnel 1 exhibited the highest ligand transport capacity. The higher bottleneck radius allows a lower energy barrier, promoting an efficient substrate and product transport. Overall, the obtained results demonstrate that DhaA from *Rhodococcus* sp. as a promising and sustainable biocatalyst for chloroform full dehalogenation, contributing to the development of novel approaches for THMs removal from drinking water.

Introduction

During the last century, progress on safe drinking water distribution were remarkable and chlorine-based disinfection played a crucial role on this achievement [1]. However, the reactive disinfectant (chlorine) in contact with natural organic matters (NOM) produces a hazardous class of pollutants, disinfection by-products (DBPs) [2]. Trihalomethanes (THM) is the most identified class of DBP in water treated with chlorine, been firstly detected in drinking water in middle 70 of last century [2]. Despite the benefits of chlorine disinfection (effective elimination of pathogens and low operational costs), the presence of THMs in drinking water has raised significant environmental and health concerns. Several processes have been applied for the removal of THMs from water, including physical-chemical and biological-based techniques [3]. Among these methods, bioremediation represents a sustainable and effective approach for the removal of THMs after they are formed. *Rhodococcus* sp. is a genus of actinomycetes (gram-positive bacteria) that display the ability to treat effluents contaminated by THMs with high efficiency while performing more eco-friendly operations (with reduced production of residues and by-products) [4]. The *Rhodococcus* sp. mechanism of THMs removal is promoted by Haloalkane dehalogenase DhaA, which is a highly active enzyme for halogenated substrates in bacterial metabolic pathways [5]. Therefore, *Rhodococcus* sp. can be a viable and sustainable source of biocatalysts that allow the removal of THMs from drinking water. Thus, this study aim identifies the potential of DhaA from *Rhodococcus* sp. as biocatalyst for THMs removal from drinking water. For this, a computational protocol using enzymatic tunnel/access prediction and molecular docking analysis of substrate/products was applied.

Methods

The three-dimensional structure of DhaA from *Rhodococcus* sp. was obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB: 1bn6) and uploaded to the CaverWeb 1.0 web server [6] for the identification of tunnels. The tunnels were identified using the

default configuration, and then filtered based on their bottleneck radius (Å) and length (Å). The most promising tunnels were selected for ligand transport analysis. The binding energies of each ligand (water, chloroform, dichloromethane, chloromethanediol, hydrochloric acid and orthoformic acid) were calculated using the reaction sequence of a complete dehalogenation using DhaA as biocatalyst (THM and subproducts) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Chloroform catalytic dehalogenation using DhaA from *Rhodococcus* sp. as biocatalyst.

Results

The identification of enzymatic tunnels in the DhaA structure was carried out, aimed at determining the efficiency of enzymatic dehalogenation of chloroform. DhaA presented four possible tunnels that extend from the enzyme surface to the catalytic site (ASP106, GLU130 and HIS272). However, two of these tunnels displayed unfavorable characteristics for substrate and product transportation (e.g., long length that hindered substance transport). The most favorable tunnels for ligand transport are described in Figure 2. The identified tunnels display similar lengths ($\approx 13\text{Å}$). However, tunnel 1 exhibited the highest substance transport capacity due to higher bottleneck

radius (1.8Å). In fact, tunnels in different DhaAs were previously studied using molecular dynamics simulations [5]. According to the authors, DhaAs have two predominant tunnels: the main tunnel, responsible for substance entry and exit, and the slot tunnel, which supports product release in the reaction.

Figure 2. Tunnels in the crystal structure of DhaA: (A) Overall structure of DhaA with two predominant tunnels, (B) DhaA main tunnel (blue) and slot tunnel (red).

The dehalogenation reaction occurs through the nucleophilic attack of ASP106 on chloroform in the presence of water. Therefore, the identification of the binding energies chloroform and water through Tunnels 1 and 2 was performed. Figure 3 depicts the trajectory of chloroform and water from the DhaA surface to the active site. The transport of chloroform and water was accomplished with lower energetic barriers through Tunnel 1.

Figure 3. Ligand trajectory from DhaA surface into the active site using tunnel 1: (A) Chloroform and (B) Water.

In the second reaction step, the product formed (dichloromethanol) is hydrolyzed, and chloromethanediol is formed. Thus, a binding energy analysis was performed for these two compounds only at the active site, as the reaction occurs in a sequence and the products are not released until full dehalogenation is achieved. Based on the results, the binding energy of the substrates studied on the active site of DhaA

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increased in the following order: chloromethanediol < dichloromethanol < chloroform. The presence of more halogen atoms increases the binding energy to the enzyme active site. After complete dehalogenation, the products formed are orthoformic acid and hydrochloric acid. Therefore, the trajectory of these compounds from the active site of DhaA to the enzyme surface was investigated using tunnels 1 and 2. Figure 4 displays the energy profile of orthoformic acid and hydrochloric acid trajectory from DhaA active site to enzyme surface using tunnel 1. The results obtained show the same behavior observed for the chloroform and water. Tunnel 1 allows a lower energy barrier and facilitates the transport of substrate and product from dehalogenation.

Figure 4. Ligand trajectory from DhaA active site to enzyme surface using tunnel 1: (A) Orthoformic acid and (B) Hydrochloric acid.

Conclusion

The enzymatic tunnels of DhaA from *Rhodococcus* sp. were identified and the efficiency of enzymatic dehalogenation of chloroform was evaluated. According to DhaA structure analysis, four possible tunnels provide access to small molecules from the enzyme surface to the catalytic active site. However, only two (the main tunnel and the slot tunnel) were favorable for ligand transport due to their shorter length and higher bottleneck radius. Molecular docking simulations showed that Tunnel 1 allows chloroform and water transport with lower energetic barriers. The binding energy analysis of products formed by each dehalogenation reaction step into DhaA active site shown that the presence of more halogen atoms increases the binding energy (more stability of an enzyme-substrate complex). Finally, the trajectory analysis of orthoformic acid and hydrochloric acid displayed a lower energy barrier for transport through Tunnel 1. The results obtained reveal that DhaA from *Rhodococcus* sp. is a promising biocatalyst for complete dehalogenation of THMs, that could be further applied for removal of THMs from drinking water.

Computer-Aided Identification of Trihalomethane Degradation by Haloalkane dehalogenase DhaA from *Rhodococcus* sp.

H2OforAll

Matheus M. Pereira^{1,*}, Rui C. Martins¹

¹ University of Coimbra, CIEPQPF – Chemical Engineering Processes and Forest Products Research Center, Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Sciences and Technology, Rua Sílvio Lima, Polo II, 3030-790 Coimbra, Portugal
*matheus@eq.uc.pt

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